

Enhancing Chatbot Responses through Improved T5 Model Incorporating Aggregated Multi-Head Attention Mechanism and Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence (AI) chatbots have become indispensable for natural language interaction, with transformer-based models driving advances in conversational agent (CA) systems. While state-of-the-art models like RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, and GPT-3 have achieved remarkable context understanding and response generation, they still face limitations. These include challenges with context retention over extended interactions, syntactic ambiguities, and bias propagation from training data, raising concerns for ethical and interpretable AI systems. This research proposes an advanced transformer model, the Improved T5 (IT5), designed to address these issues. IT5 integrates Aggregated Multi-Head Attention (AMHA) and Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) into the T5 framework to improve context retention, response nuance, and bias reduction. Additionally, a retraining mechanism updates IT5's knowledge base with every 50 new question-answer pairs, ensuring fairness and relevance in chatbot responses. The model's performance was rigorously tested on the NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets, where IT5 achieved top BLEU scores of 0.7533, 0.7012, 0.7155, and 0.7373, respectively. It consistently demonstrated lower WER scores of 0.1957, 0.2106, 0.2254, and 0.1953, and higher ROUGE-L scores of 0.8875, 0.8991, 0.8731, and 0.8933 across these datasets. IT5 also exceeded in accuracy (0.98, 0.97, 0.96, 0.97), precision (0.96, 0.98, 0.97, 0.96), recall (0.95, 0.96, 0.97, 0.98), and F1 scores (0.95, 0.98, 0.96, 0.96), surpassing six state-of-the-art models, namely RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, and GPT-3. The findings demonstrate IT5's superior ability to generate meaningful, fair, and high-quality responses, establishing it as a frontrunner for robust and ethical conversational AI across various applications.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Chatbot, Improved T5 Model, Aggregated Multi-Head Attention Mechanism, Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory

Categories: I, I.2.7, I.2, J

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1 Introduction

Chatbots, abbreviated from chat robots, embody AI applications designed for natural language conversations. Positioned at the confluence of Machine Learning (ML), Natural Language Processing (NLP), and user interface design, they represent a

transformative technology [Grassi et al., 2022]. These intelligent virtual agents simulate human-like interactions, providing immediate responses and assistance across various platforms [Ahmad et al., 2022; Balakrishnan & Dwivedi, 2021; L. Zhang et al., 2020]. Chatbots aim to streamline communication and automate tasks, delivering users a seamless and efficient means to interact with digital systems. Their applications extend to customer service, information retrieval, e-commerce transactions, and acting as personal assistants [Cai et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2021; Popp et al., 2022]. The underlying technology often relies on ML algorithms that enable chatbots to interpret and address user queries [Mokmin & Ibrahim, 2021]. Rule-based systems and advanced models, such as transformer-based architectures, contribute to their ability to comprehend context, ensuring more meaningful interactions [A & N, 2024; Lincy & Gayathri, 2022; Madanan et al., 2023]. As chatbot capabilities advance, they are essential for enhancing user experiences, increasing efficiency, and transforming how businesses and individuals engage with technology. Ongoing advancements in AI and NLP further contribute to the continued growth and sophistication of chatbot applications across diverse domains.

1.1 Background

Recent breakthroughs in NLP are largely due to the creation of transformer-based models, which have greatly enhanced conversational agent (CA) systems. Notable advancements include models like BART (Bidirectional and Auto-Regressive Transformers) [Chang et al., 2023] and GPT-3 (Generative Pre-trained Transformer-3) [Namitha et al., 2024] exemplify this shift. These models leverage self-attention techniques to handle input sequences in parallel, effectively managing contextual information and overcoming limitations inherent in traditional Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). RNNs handle data step by step, but they often struggle with understanding long-term connections. Transformers, on the other hand, use multi-head self-attention to analyze how words relate to each other in a sequence. This design helps them understand complex relationships and process data faster by working on multiple parts at once. In CA systems, transformers are especially good at grasping context and creating meaningful replies. Through comprehensive pre-training on diverse datasets, these models gain a profound grasp of language subtleties, enabling them to adapt to a wide range of conversational contexts. Moreover, transformers support fine-tuning with domain-specific data, enhancing their versatility across applications. The adaptability and effectiveness of transformer-based models have led to widespread adoption in developing advanced CAs, fostering more natural and contextually aware interactions between users and virtual assistants.

1.2 Problem Statement

Despite the significant advancements that transformer-based models have brought to NLP in recent years, they still exhibit critical limitations that can affect their overall effectiveness and applicability. Pre-trained language models often inherit and propagate biases from their training data, leading to biased responses, particularly in scenarios where fairness and unbiased interactions are crucial. This raises ethical concerns, especially in applications requiring interpretable and equitable outputs. Furthermore, these models frequently struggle with resolving syntactic ambiguities,

particularly when sentences contain multiple valid interpretations, which can impair their overall performance. Additionally, many models have limitations in understanding context during multi-turn interactions, risking the propagation of misunderstandings and leading to undesirable outcomes. Overall, the reduced interpretability of these models poses challenges in comprehending broader contexts during text understanding, further hindering their effectiveness.

1.3 Motivation

This research is motivated by the notable limitations identified in transformer-based models. These challenges have been critically observed in their application to NLP. Despite their advancements, transformer-based models often inherit and propagate biases from their training data, leading to biased responses that raise ethical concerns in applications requiring fairness and interpretability. Additionally, they struggle with resolving syntactic ambiguities and maintaining contextual understanding during multi-turn interactions, which can result in misunderstandings and reduced performance. Furthermore, their complexity often hinders interpretability, complicating broader context comprehension. Therefore, addressing these issues is essential to improve the fairness, accuracy, and effectiveness of transformer models, especially in real-world situations where ethics play a crucial role.

1.4 Contributions of the Proposed Research

This research introduces a new IT5 model (Improved T5 (Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer)) that combines the AMHA mechanism, BiLSTM, and a retraining process to overcome major shortcomings in transformer-based models. The major contributions are as follows:

- **AMHA Mechanism:** The AMHA mechanism is incorporated into both the encoder and decoder, enhancing information retention and interpretability in prolonged conversations. This application improves response generation, ensuring outputs maintain contextual relevance and incorporate greater depth.
- **BiLSTM Integration:** BiLSTM layers are utilized within both the encoder and decoder components to produce feature-rich outputs, elevating the ability of the model to capture nuanced contextual details and enhance the quality of responses.
- **Knowledge Update Mechanism:** A systematic retraining process is initiated for every set of 50 new question-answer pairs. This updates the model's knowledge and reduces the propagation of biased responses, thereby improving fairness and relevance.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 examines the transformer model, focusing on its ability to generate meaningful responses. Section 3 delves into the theoretical underpinnings and core sequence of actions of the proposed IT5 model, involving the collection of the question-answer dataset. Section 4 assesses and contrasts the performance of the proposed IT5 framework with other pertinent research efforts. Finally, in Section 5, a summary is presented, along with potential avenues for improving the proposed methodology.

2 Related Research on the Development of CAs

Table 1 offers an overview of related works that concentrate on the development of CAs. It outlines various studies, highlighting the datasets/models used, vectorization or word embedding techniques, training methodologies, and the key contributions made in advancing CA technology.

Reference	Dataset /Model Used	Vectorization /Word Embedding	Training Methodology	Key Contribution
[Bird et al., 2021]	Custom Social Interaction Dataset	Numerical vector of predictions analyzed via relative entropy	RoBERTa	Chatbot Interaction with AI (CI-AI) framework with artificial paraphrasing achieved good accuracy using RoBERTa, showcasing improved chatbot interaction through augmented training data.
[Park et al., 2023]	Java Datasets	Positional Embeddings	Aligned Lexical and Syntactic information-Transformer (ALSI-Transformer)	This study introduces the ALSI-Transformer, utilizing aligned lexical and syntactic details to excel in generating code comments with existing results.
[Qi et al., 2022]	General Multimodal Sentiment Analysis Datasets	Multimodal embeddings	Multimodal Encoding-Decoding Network with Transformer (MEDN-Transformer)	A network was created to handle long-term connections across different types of data, reducing the effect of non-language data on the accuracy of language data to enhance predictions of emotional outcomes.
[Z. Zhang et al., 2022]	Cornell Dialogue Corpus	Absolute Positional Encoding	Syntax-Guided Network Transformer (SG-Net Transformer)	Enhanced linguistic representation using Syntactic Dependency of Interest (SDOI)

				in self-attention networks.
[Chang et al., 2023]	NYT and WebNLG	Positional Encoding	BART	Proposed a generative JERE framework using BART for enhanced extraction of entity-relation triplets, achieving cutting-edge results
[Namitha et al., 2024]	Custom text data	Binary encoding	GPT-3	Developed a secure linguistic steganography approach with GPT-3, achieving low detection rates and robust encoding
[Gargiulo et al., 2022]	OntoNotes	High-dimensional word embeddings with context-dependent boundary representations; LSTM-based e2e-coref model; ELMO for word representation in c2f-coref model	ELECTRA	Improved contextual representation and coreference resolution using ELECTRA; superior performance in token and span representation.
[Sams & Zahra, 2023]	Indonesian song dataset	Concatenation of audio and text classifier outputs into a fusion vector	CNN-LSTM for audio (mel spectrogram), XLNet for lyrics; Stacking ensemble method with ANN	Achieved 80.56% accuracy; Multimodal MER system outperformed single-modal approaches
[Shang et al., 2020]	SQuAD	Glove Embeddings	Multilayer Transformer Aggregation Encoder	AG-MTA, an answer generation model, uses multi-layer attention transformer aggregation and novel positional encoding to attain leading-edge performance
[Mohsan et al., 2023]	Indiana University Chest X-Ray dataset	Patch Embeddings	Vision Transformer	Improved response relevance and coherence through attention mechanisms, revolutionizing language understanding

				and fostering context-aware chatbot interactions.
[Gong et al., 2022; Honda & Hagiwara, 2019; Palasundram et al., 2020, 2021]	Multiple datasets: SQuAD, NarrativeQA, Commonsense Conversation Dataset, and Quasar-T Dataset	TF-IDF, Word2Vector	Seq2Seq model	Popular framework for training chatbots in generating responses.
[Gu et al., 2020]	Multiple datasets: Ubuntu Dialogue Corpus V1 and Ubuntu Dialogue Corpus V2, Douban Conversation Corpus and E-commerce Dialogue Corpus	GloVe Embeddings	Utterance-to-Utterance Model	This article introduces U2U-IMN, a novel utterance-level interactive matching network achieving leading performance in multi-turn response selection
[Hsu & Chang, 2021; Wang et al., 2022]	Covid-19 Symptom dataset, Open dataset	TF-IDF, Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI)	ML and Deep Learning (DL)	Focus on response generation using ML and DL methodologies.
[Ait-Mlouk & Jiang, 2020; Socratianurak et al., 2021]	myPersonality dataset, Law Dataset	TF-IDF	DL models	Application of TF-IDF for effective word vectorization in chatbot training.
[de Arriba-Pérez et al., 2022; Miura et al., 2022; Ouerhani et al., 2022; Polignano et al., 2020; Rathnayaka et al., 2022]	Medical Datasets	TF-IDF, Word2Vector	Rule based approach	In these studies, healthcare chatbots have been developed to provide solutions for patient engagement, symptom analysis, and health advice.

Table 1: Related works focusing on development of CAs

2.1 Literature Employing Transformer Model for response generation

[Bird et al., 2021], in their pioneering work, proposed the CI-AI framework, an innovative approach that leverages artificial paraphrasing to enrich human-labeled data, boosting task classification for transformer-based chatbots. By augmenting training data with the T5 model, their study shows a 4.01% average accuracy gain, with RoBERTa achieving 97.6%. However, while CI-AI emphasizes natural interaction and improved accuracy to foster user-friendly, accessible AI, RoBERTa is susceptible to

adopting and transmitting biases from its training data. This raises ethical concerns, as such biases may lead to skewed responses, posing challenges in applications where fairness and unbiased interactions are crucial. Additionally, RoBERTa's complex representations may yield responses that are less interpretable, further impacting its applicability in sensitive contexts.

[Z. Zhang et al., 2022], in their pioneering work, emphasized the importance of effective language comprehension in AI, noting that precise modeling of linguistic intricacies is essential while minimizing irrelevant information. Traditional attentive models often falter by focusing indiscriminately on all words, overlooking contextual significance. To address this, the study advocates for syntax-guided text modeling, integrating specific syntactic constraints into attention mechanisms to enhance linguistic representations. By introducing Syntactic Dependency of Interest (SDOI) within Self-Attention Networks (SAN), the novel SG-Net enriches Transformer encoders, demonstrating improved performance on tasks like text comprehension, inferential reasoning, and translation processing. However, a key challenge with the syntax-guided transformer model lies in accurately resolving syntactic ambiguities, especially in sentences with multiple valid syntactic structures. This difficulty in correct interpretation results in parsing issues, thereby impacting overall model performance.

[Park et al., 2023], in their leading-edge study, explored automatic comment generation for computer programs, advancing prior efforts by incorporating both lexical and syntactic information from code. This led to the development of Code-Aligned Type sequences (CAT) and the ALSI-Transformer, achieving cutting-edge performance and promoting more efficient, insightful coding practices. However, the ALSI-Transformer exhibits restricted understanding of syntactic structures when handling multi-turn conversations. This limitation may cause the model to carry forward contextual restrictions, potentially leading to unintended or unfair outcomes.

[Qi et al., 2022], in their cutting-edge investigation, tackled the complex task of multimodal sentiment analysis in NLP, focusing on the use of multimodal signals such as textual data, facial movements, and audio signals in video content to interpret emotions. Their study emphasized the growing relevance of single-modality data over time and underscored the value of examining sustained dependencies across and within multiple modalities. The proposed MEDN-Transformer effectively addressed these challenges, demonstrating notable advancements and stability beyond cutting-edge models across multimodal sentiment analysis datasets. However, the model exhibits reduced interpretability, which poses challenges in grasping broader context during text comprehension in training.

[Chang et al., 2023], in his pioneering work, highlighted the importance of Joint Entity and Relation Extraction (JERE) in Information Extraction (IE). While leveraging the seq2seq BART model has shown strong performance, optimal outcomes, BART still faces significant limitations. It can propagate biases inherent in its training data, leading to potentially skewed outputs, which poses challenges for applications requiring fairness and unbiased information extraction. Additionally, BART's reduced interpretability and difficulty resolving syntactic ambiguities in complex sentences limit its effectiveness in generating reliable entity-relation triplets.

[Namitha et al., 2024], in his work, demonstrated the use of GPT-3 for linguistic steganography, showcasing its capability for secure data embedding. However, GPT-3 inherits limitations such as biases from training data, leading to skewed outputs, which pose challenges in unbiased text generation for secure applications. Additionally, GPT-

3 struggles with interpretability and managing complex, context-rich sequences, impacting its effectiveness in tasks requiring precise structure and control, such as steganography and secure communication.

3 Proposed Methodology

The proposed methodology has two main parts. The first part is the Dataset Training Module, which uses the IT5 architecture to train the dataset. Based on pre-trained knowledge, the IT5 chatbot delivers responses for live user queries. The second part is the Retraining Module, which is responsible for collecting new queries from the user and their predicted responses. If the user provides positive feedback for a particular query, both the query and its response will be added to the existing dataset, and retraining will be conducted. Figure 1 shows the structure of the proposed research.

Figure 1: Architecture of Proposed Research

3.1 Dataset Training Module

In the dataset training module, the data is initially collected and preprocessed using various techniques, including data cleaning and tokenization. Subsequently, the preprocessed data is fed into the IT5 architecture for the training process. Upon completion of the IT5 training process, a trained model is obtained as the output.

3.1.1 Data Preprocessing

In NLP, data preprocessing has played a crucial role in optimizing ML algorithms by efficiently structuring text. In the proposed research, preprocessing techniques, such as

data cleaning, and tokenization, are vital. First, data cleaning includes changing question-answer input into lowercase and removing the necessary stop words and special characters. Then, tokenization breaks sentences into individual words, an important step for text processing. These preprocessing procedures are fundamental for boosting the efficiency and performance of the ML model in managing textual data. Figure 2 represents the block diagram of data pre-processing process.

Figure 2: A block diagram illustrating the data pre-processing process

Algorithm 1: Pre-processing of the dataset

Input: A dataset comprises a collection of questions enriched with metadata and corresponding answers.

Output: A list of cleaned and normalized question-answer pairs.

for every line in the question-answer list

do

 Initialize line dictionary

 Perform line splitting using the `line.split('\n')`

 Add split id and question-answer data to the dictionary

end do

do

 Separate Questions and answers by using question-answer id and save them in a separate list

for every question in the question list and answer in the answer list

do

 Lower case conversion

 Removing special characters such as `[-()\"#@;:<>{}+=~|.?,]`

 Replacing contracted words with their respective expansion (ex: I'm as I am)

end do

end

end do

end

Algorithm 1 represents the preprocessing steps which are conducted in the proposed research. Initially, the raw question-answer datasets are gathered and then, the entire dataset is divided into several lines of text. For each question-answer data, each and every single word is obtained using data splitting. Next, as a part of the data normalization process, lowercase conversion and removal of special characters and stop words are employed. Figure 3 represents the IT5 architecture for training process.

3.1.2 IT5 Architecture for Training Process

Figure 3: IT5 Architecture

3.1.2.1 Input Representation

The IT5 model processes input as a sequence of word embeddings, where each word is represented as a high-dimensional vector.

3.1.2.2 Positional Encoding

Since the IT5 model handles words simultaneously rather than in sequence, it lacks the inherent order information present in sequential models. To mitigate this issue, input embeddings are enhanced with positional encodings to reflect the position of each word in the sequence.

3.1.2.3 Encoder

In the IT5 model, the encoder comprises multiple identical layers arranged in sequence, each consisting of two main elements: the AMHA mechanism and the BiLSTM. The AMHA mechanism helps the model figure out the importance of different words in the input sequence in relation to the current word. Additionally, the connected BiLSTM network operates independently at each position in the sequence. The encoder block also includes an Add&Norm component, responsible for performing addition and layer normalization.

3.1.2.4 Decoder

The decoder of the IT5 model has made up of several identical layers, each containing three main components: the Masked Multi-Head Attention (MMHA) mechanism, the AMHA mechanism, and BiLSTM. The MMHA mechanism stops the model from attending to future positions, making sure it only focuses on positions before the current one. The AMHA mechanism and BiLSTM function similarly to an encoder.

3.1.2.5 AMHA Mechanism

In the proposed IT5 model, the AMHA mechanism is a crucial component that allows the model to grasp various facets of relationships among words in a sequence. It was introduced to enhance the flexibility of the attention mechanism, allowing the model to address multiple components and positions within the input sequence simultaneously. Figure 4 represents the architecture of the proposed AMHA mechanism. The AMHA mechanism is comprised of three instances of the Multi-Head Attention (MHA) mechanism. The MHA mechanism builds upon the concept of attention by incorporating multiple attention heads working in parallel. Each attention head is trained to focus on different facets of the relationships between words. In the processing of each attention head, three distinct linear projections are applied to the input embeddings, effectively projecting them onto query, key, and value vectors. These projections are denoted as matrices WQ , WK , and WV . Each attention head calculates attention weights independently, by utilizing the corresponding projected query, key, and value vectors.

Figure 4: Architecture of AMHA Mechanism

The results from the three MHA mechanisms are then aggregated using a mean function to fine-tune the ultimate output. Let us consider an input sequence X and the projections for the i-th attention head (Q_i, K_i, V_i), the attention output (A_i) for that head is computed as follows.

$$A_i = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{Q_i K_i^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V_i \tag{1}$$

In Equ. (1), d_k refers to the size of the key vectors. The softmax function calculates attention weights, which are applied to scale the values (V_i) accordingly.

The final output of AMHA mechanism can be computed as,

$$F_{out} = \text{mean}(MHA_1, MHA_2, MHA_3) \tag{2}$$

In Equ. (2), F_{out} represent the Final output of the AMHA mechanism, $MHA_1, MHA_2,$ and MHA_3 represents the output of three MHA layers.

3.1.2.6 BiLSTM

BiLSTM is a variation of RNN that excels at handling sequential information. In text classification tasks, BiLSTM facilitates the consideration of both preceding and following context during predictions. This helps the model discern patterns and relationships in the sequence from both directions. By examining the text in a bidirectional manner, the model is able to capture a variety of features, such as contextual nuances and long-range dependencies. The BiLSTM can create a richer representation of the input text by combining information from both directions, resulting in enhanced performance in text classification tasks compared to conventional unidirectional LSTM models. Figure 5 represents the architecture of BiLSTM.

Figure 5: BiLSTM

BiLSTM consists of three main components: the forward layer, backward layer, and an activation layer. The forward and backward layers handle the input sequence in one direction, either from the beginning to the end (forward layer) or from the end to the beginning (backward layer). The outputs from both the forward and backward layers are typically combined in some way to provide a thorough understanding of the input sequence.

- **Forward Layer**

The forward layer of BiLSTM processes the input sequence in a conventional forward direction, identifying temporal relationships and patterns as it progresses from the beginning to the end of the sequence. The forward layer retains information about the past context and contributes to understanding the sequential patterns in the data from the beginning of the time steps to the end.

- **Backward Layer**

The backward layer operates on the input sequence in the reverse order, starting from the end and moving towards the beginning. This capability allows BiLSTM to identify dependencies and patterns in the input sequence from the end to the beginning as well. The backward layer retains information about the future context and contributes to understanding the sequential patterns in the data from the final time steps to the initial time steps.

- **Activation Layer**

The activation function within each LSTM cell controls the dissemination of data through the network. The activation layer, in the context of BiLSTMs, applies an activation function to the combined output from both the forward and backward layers. This combined output gathers the data from both directions and provides a more comprehensive representation of the

initial sequence, which is then passed to the subsequent layers in the network for further processing.

The combination of forward and backward layers in BiLSTM enables the network to effectively analyze contextual details from both earlier and later parts of the sequence. This dual perspective enhances the model's ability to comprehensively understand the input sequence, leading to more accurate classifications. During the training phase of the chatbot in the proposed model, the AdaDelta optimization algorithm is employed to fine-tune the loss function concerning the model's weights.

- **AdaDelta Optimizer**

AdaDelta is an optimization algorithm specifically designed to train neural networks efficiently. This algorithm extends the concept of adaptive learning rates initially presented in AdaGrad. AdaDelta is notably innovative in its approach, aiming to overcome certain drawbacks associated with AdaGrad, specifically the issue of learning rates decreasing monotonically over time. Equations characterizing the operation of the AdaDelta are represented below.

- **Running Average Squared Gradients ($E[g^2]_t$)**

$$E[g^2]_t = \rho E[g^2]_{t-1} + (1 - \rho)g_t^2 \quad (3)$$

In Equ. (3), where ρ represents the decay rate (typically chosen to be close to 1), and g_t^2 denotes the squared gradient at time t .

- **Root Mean Square (RMS) of Parameter Updates ($RMS[\Delta_x]_{t-1}$)**

$$RMS[\Delta_x]_{t-1} = \sqrt{E[\Delta x^2]_{t-1} + \epsilon} \quad (4)$$

In Equ. (4), where $E[\Delta x^2]_{t-1}$ signifies the running average of squared parameter updates up to time $t - 1$, and ϵ represents a small constant added to ensure numerical stability.

- **Parameter Update (Δx_t)**

$$\Delta x_t = \frac{RMS[\Delta x]_{t-1}}{RMS[g]_t} * g_t \quad (5)$$

In Equ. (5), where g_t denotes the gradient at time t , and $RMS[g]_t$ represents the root mean square of gradients at time t .

These Eqs. (3), (4) and (5) capture the essence of AdaDelta's adaptability, wherein the learning rates dynamically adjust based on historical information derived from gradients and parameter updates during the training process.

3.1.2.7 Layer Normalization and Residual Connections

In both the encoder and decoder, each sub-layer (such as attention and BiLSTM) employs layer normalization and includes residual connections to improve training stability and enable the model to learn more effectively.

3.1.2.8 Output Layer

The decoder's final output is processed through a linear transformation followed by a softmax function to produce a probability distribution over the vocabulary, corresponding to each position in the output sequence.

Algorithm 2: Training preprocessed data using IT5 Architecture

Input: Pre-processed data

Output: Trained Model

Initialize: max_training_iteration = 100, learning_rate = 0.001, dropout rate = 0.4, d_model = 512, layer_norm_eps = 1e-5, num_heads = 8.

Initialize training_iteration = 0

Add positional encodings to preprocessed input embeddings.

while training_iteration < max_training_iterations:

for each training set:

do

 Pass input through the encoder to obtain encoder outputs.

 Use encoder outputs for masked self-attention in the decoder
(for autoregressive decoding).

 Using the decoder, predict the subsequent token within the sequence.

 Compute loss between predicted sequence and target sequence.

end do

end

 Compute gradients concerning model parameters.

 Adjust model parameters utilizing the AdaDelta optimizer.

 training_iteration += 1

 # Validation

if training_iteration % validation_interval == 0:

 Evaluate the model on a validation dataset.

if the criteria for early stopping are met:

do

 break #Early stopping

end do

 compute current validation loss

if current validation loss < previous validation loss:

do

 Save the model as a checkpoint

end do

 previous validation loss = current validation loss

Algorithm 2 represents the training process of IT5 architecture. It begins with the initialization of the model parameters, encompassing both the encoder and decoder weights. Subsequently, the data preparation phase involves positional encodings to capture the sequential order of tokens. Cross-entropy is selected as a loss function. The AdaDelta optimizer is utilized to adjust the parameters of the IT5 model during the training process. The training is carried out within a loop structure, allowing the IT5 model to complete multiple iterations. Within each iteration, a forward pass involves passing the input through the encoder to obtain outputs. These outputs are subsequently used for MMHA in the decoder, after which the next token is predicted and the loss is calculated. During the backward pass, gradients are calculated, and the model parameters are refined using the specified optimizer. The training loop includes periodic validation steps to evaluate performance, with an if statement to monitor validation results and implement early stopping if necessary. The model parameters are stored periodically throughout the training process, and hyperparameters are fine-tuned based on validation results. Finally, the trained model undergoes evaluation on a test dataset, completing the training process.

3.2 Retraining Module

In the retraining module, the retraining process is initiated upon the successful completion of every 50 response pairs. This strategic decision ensures that the model undergoes adaptation and improvement at regular intervals, particularly when it has demonstrated proficiency in generating accurate responses. The successful response pairs refer to instances where the model outputs the desired and intended results. When the cumulative count of these successful response pairs reaches a multiple of 50, the retraining module is triggered. Figure 6 depicts the process flow of the retraining module. The flowchart illustrates the sequential steps and dependencies within the IT5-based retraining module. Each box in the flowchart signifies a distinct stage in the process, outlining the specific actions undertaken during the retraining phase. The user's query is first collected, and the response is generated using the IT5 pre-trained model, after which user feedback is gathered on the generated response. If the feedback for the generated response is positive, the input query and generated response are appended to the existing database. When the IT5 chatbot has successfully delivered 50 satisfactory responses, the chatbot initiates the retraining process by utilizing both the existing and newly added data. On the other hand, if the IT5 chatbot has not yet provided 50 satisfactory responses, it returns to reading the user input to further refine its responses.

Figure 6: Flow Chart of Retraining Module

4 Result and Discussion

4.1 Experimental Settings

The proposed research is implemented using Python 3.12 and Tensorflow version 2.13.0 in Spyder IDE. Datasets such as NarrativeQA (Hugging Face, n.d.-c), SQuAD (Hugging Face, n.d.-d), MS MARCO (Hugging Face, n.d.-b), and InsuranceQA (Hugging Face, n.d.-a) are utilized for training the proposed model. The information about the NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets is illustrated in Table 2.

Dataset Name	NarrativeQA	SQuAD	MS MARCO	InsuranceQA
Dataset Summary	It is a fiction-based dataset composed of English words	It is a crowdsourced dataset sourced from Wikipedia articles	It is a large-scale dataset for machine reading and question answering derived from real-world data.	A dataset specifically focused on insurance-related questions and answers.
Total Samples	41,180	49,960	49,686	39,346
Training (80%) (Number of question-answer pairs)	32944	39,968	39748	31476
Validation (10%)	4118	4996	4968	3938
Testing (10%)	4118	1996	4968	3938
Maximum question length	20	20	22	24
Maximum answer length	20	20	22	24

Table 2: Dataset Information

Dataset Name	Category	Total Samples	Training (80%)	Validation (10%)	Testing (10%)
NarrativeQA	Factual	19800	15840	1980	1980
	Conceptual	21380	17104	2138	2138
SQuAD	Who	11570	9256	1157	1157
	What	12450	9960	1245	1245
	Why	12790	10232	1279	1279
	How	13150	10520	1315	1315
MS MARCO	Factoid	15990	12792	1599	1599
	Passage	16580	13264	1658	1658
	Abstractive	17116	13692	1711	1711
InsuranceQA	Claims	12956	10364	1295	1295
	Policies	13190	10552	1319	1319
	Other	13200	10560	1320	1320

Table 3: Categorical Distribution and Dataset Splits

Table 3 represents the categorical distribution and dataset splits for the datasets used in this study. The datasets consist of diverse and well-distributed categories. For instance, MS MARCO and InsuranceQA are organized into categories such as Factoid, Passage, Abstractive, Claims, Policies, and Other, which were inferred based on the nature of the tasks they address. While SQuAD derives question type categories from the question structures (e.g., "Who," "What," "Why," "How"), these were inferred based on the question types. NarrativeQA, however, focuses on question-answer pairs derived from narrative text, with two categories, Factual and Conceptual, formed through analysis of the question structures. These derived distributions ensure a balanced representation of data across categories. For evaluation, each dataset was split

into 80% for training, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing, ensuring the structure remained intact. This approach provides a stable and reliable foundation for model training and evaluation.

Parameter	Value
Number of Epochs	100
Training Batch Size	32 pairs
The dimensionality of the model's hidden states	512
Learning Rate	0.001
Dropout Rate	0.4
The epsilon value for layer normalization	1e-5
The number of attention heads utilized within the MHA mechanisms	8
Maximum Sequence Length	512 tokens
Warm-up Steps	20000
Weight Decay	0.1
Gradient Clipping Threshold	1.0
Optimizer	AdaDelta
Learning Rate Scheduler	Cosine Annealing
Initialization Method	Glorot uniform initialization
Attention Dropout Rate	0.2
Activation Function	GeLU (Gaussian Error Linear Unit)
Hidden Layer Initialization Range	[-0.01, 0.01]
Embedding Dimension	512 (dimensionality of word embeddings)

Table 4: Parameters of the proposed model

First Pair	
Question	Why does King Leopold force Barney to leave Lutha?
Answer	He discovers Barney's love for Princess Emma.
Second Pair	
Question	What is seen by Lindsey during an investigation of the USS Montana?
Answer	A strange light surrounds the submarine.

Table 5: Representative Question-Answer Pairs Employed in Training for Answer Generation

Table 4 represents the important parameters initialized to train the proposed model, and Table 5 illustrates the representative question-answer pairs used in training for answer generation.

4.2 Evaluation of Proposed Model

In the proposed research, seven evaluation metrics, namely the Bilingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU) score and the Word Error Rate (WER), ROUGE-L Score (Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation), Accuracy score, Precision score, Recall score, and F1 score, are employed to evaluate and measure the performance of the proposed IT5 architecture that utilizes the AMHA Mechanism and BiLSTM.

4.2.1 BLEU

The BLEU metric stands out as the most widely used measure in the field of answer generation. Its main use lies in evaluating the accuracy of translations generated by both human translators and computer systems. The BLEU metric assesses precision by comparing N-gram overlaps between two sequences, while also applying penalties to machine-generated text that is shorter than its human-generated equivalent. Beyond its original purpose, BLEU has found extensive use in evaluating Natural Answer Generation (NAG) tasks and is recognized for its robust correlation with human quality assessments. This metric effectively gauges the accuracy of the systems being evaluated, yielding scores within the range of 0 to 1. Higher BLEU scores indicate improved model performance, suggesting that the generated responses closely align with the topic.

4.2.2 WER

The WER is utilized to evaluate the model's limitations by calculating the ratio of incorrectly generated words to the total words. Scores range from 0 to 1, where lower scores signify fewer errors, reflecting an improvement in the model's ability to generate accurate and relevant outputs.

$$WER = \frac{\sum WC_{wrong}}{\sum WC_{total}} \quad (6)$$

In Equ. (6), WC_{wrong} represents the wrongly generated word count, and WC_{total} represents the total generated word count.

4.2.3 ROUGE-L

ROUGE-L measures the quality of machine-generated text in tasks like summarization and translation. The 'L' refers to the Longest Common Subsequence (LCS) method, which evaluates the overlap between generated content and reference text. It emphasizes the longest matching sequences, providing insights into how closely the output mirrors the intended text.

4.2.4 Accuracy Score

Accuracy measures the percentage of correctly classified instances compared to the total instances in the dataset.

$$Accuracy = \frac{(TPV + TNV)}{(TPV + TNV + FPV + FNV)} \quad (7)$$

In Equ. (7), TPV stands for the True Positive value, TNV stands for the True Negative value, FPV stands for the False Positive value, and FNV stands for the False Negative value.

4.2.5 Precision Score

Precision measures the proportion of true positives out of all positive predictions, indicating how effectively the model identifies relevant data points. Equ. (8) represents the formulae to calculate the precision score.

$$Precision = \frac{(TPV)}{(TPV + FPV)} \quad (8)$$

4.2.6 Recall Score

Recall represents the proportion of true positives relative to all actual positive cases, showcasing the model's ability to capture all relevant data in a dataset. Equ. (9) represents the formulae to calculate the recall score.

$$Recall = \frac{(TPV)}{(TPV + FNV)} \quad (9)$$

4.2.7 F1 Score

The F1 score calculates the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balanced evaluation of these two metrics. This measure is particularly effective for evaluating performance in scenarios with imbalanced class distributions. Equ. (10) represents the formulae to calculate the f1 score.

$$F1 = 2 * \frac{(Precision * Recall)}{(Precision + Recall)} \quad (10)$$

4.3 Evaluation Results

Techniques that are utilized in the IT5 architecture are the AMHA mechanism and BiLSTM. The training is conducted for NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets, and the optimal result of each dataset model is taken for performance comparison with state-of-the-art models such as RoBERTa [Bird et al., 2021], ALSI-Transformer [Park et al., 2023], MEDN-Transformer [Qi et al., 2022], SG-Net Transformer Model (SG-Net) [Z. Zhang et al., 2022], BART [Chang et al., 2023], and GPT-3 [Namitha et al., 2024].

Metrics	Model	NarrativeQA	SQuAD	MS MARCO	InsuranceQA
BLEU	RoBERTa	0.5398	0.5086	0.5652	0.5232
	ALSI-Transformer	0.5708	0.6768	0.6276	0.6481
	MEDN-Transformer	0.5664	0.5287	0.5791	0.5531
	SG-Net Transformer	0.5718	0.6127	0.6010	0.6124
	BART	0.6923	0.6645	0.6720	0.7123
	GPT-3	0.7154	0.6905	0.6949	0.7193
	IT5 (proposed)	0.7533	0.7012	0.7155	0.7373
	RoBERTa	0.3702	0.4146	0.3134	0.3353
	ALSI-Transformer	0.3493	0.2894	0.3393	0.3918
	MEDN-Transformer	0.3324	0.4354	0.4175	0.4476

WER	SG-Net Transformer	0.3301	0.2719	0.3125	0.3516
	BART	0.2638	0.2428	0.2517	0.2699
	GPT-3	0.2213	0.2394	0.2495	0.2212
	IT5 (proposed)	0.1957	0.2106	0.2254	0.1953
ROUGE-L	RoBERTa	0.6272	0.6790	0.7146	0.6127
	ALSI-Transformer	0.8347	0.8151	0.7951	0.8018
	MEDN-Transformer	0.7142	0.7353	0.7758	0.7315
	SG-Net Transformer	0.8124	0.7916	0.7546	0.7815
	BART	0.8512	0.8635	0.8421	0.8514
	GPT-3	0.8617	0.8726	0.8521	0.8634
	IT5 (proposed)	0.8875	0.8991	0.8731	0.8933
Accuracy	RoBERTa	0.86	0.82	0.84	0.88
	ALSI-Transformer	0.94	0.95	0.85	0.86
	MEDN-Transformer	0.91	0.90	0.86	0.84
	SG-Net Transformer	0.93	0.92	0.87	0.85
	BART	0.95	0.94	0.91	0.90
	GPT-3	0.96	0.95	0.93	0.94
	IT5 (proposed)	0.98	0.97	0.96	0.97
Precision	RoBERTa	0.84	0.82	0.86	0.85
	ALSI-Transformer	0.92	0.93	0.90	0.88
	MEDN-Transformer	0.89	0.90	0.94	0.91
	SG-Net Transformer	0.90	0.91	0.93	0.92
	BART	0.92	0.93	0.92	0.92
	GPT-3	0.94	0.96	0.94	0.93
	IT5 (proposed)	0.96	0.98	0.97	0.96
Recall	RoBERTa	0.82	0.83	0.84	0.87
	ALSI-Transformer	0.90	0.91	0.90	0.96
	MEDN-Transformer	0.86	0.87	0.88	0.90
	SG-Net Transformer	0.91	0.90	0.92	0.95
	BART	0.91	0.92	0.91	0.93
	GPT-3	0.93	0.95	0.93	0.95
	IT5 (proposed)	0.95	0.96	0.97	0.98
F1 Score	RoBERTa	0.82	0.81	0.84	0.86
	ALSI-Transformer	0.91	0.91	0.89	0.91
	MEDN-Transformer	0.87	0.88	0.90	0.90
	SG-Net Transformer	0.90	0.90	0.92	0.90

	BART	0.91	0.92	0.91	0.92
	GPT-3	0.93	0.95	0.93	0.94
	IT5 (proposed)	0.95	0.98	0.96	0.96

Table 6: Evaluation results of IT5 vs State-of-the-art models

Table 6 represents the evaluation metrics for models in Transformer architecture such as RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, GPT-3 and IT5.

4.3.1 BLEU Scores

Figure 7: BLEU Score

Figure 7 compares 3D bar plots of BLEU scores for the NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets across seven algorithms: RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, GPT-3, and the IT5 architecture. The proposed IT5 architecture demonstrated superior performance, achieving a BLEU score of 0.7533 on the NarrativeQA dataset, surpassing state-of-the-art benchmarks. Additionally, it achieved scores of 0.7012 for SQuAD, 0.7155 for MS MARCO, and 0.7373 for the InsuranceQA dataset.

4.3.2 WER Scores

Figure 8: WER Score

Figure 8 illustrates a comparison of 3D bar plots showing WER scores for the NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets across seven algorithms: RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, GPT-3, and the IT5 architecture. Among these, the proposed IT5 architecture achieved WER scores of 0.1957, outperforming state-of-the-art models. It recorded 0.2106 for SQuAD, 0.2245 for MS MARCO, and 0.1953 for InsuranceQA, with lower WER scores indicating better performance.

4.3.3 ROUGE-L Scores

Figure 9: ROUGE-L Score

Figure 9 represents a comparison of 3D bar plots illustrating ROUGE-L scores for NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets across seven algorithms: RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, GPT-3, and the IT5 architecture. Among these algorithms, the innovative IT5 architecture achieved a ROUGE-L score of 0.8875, outperforming the scores of advanced models available. Similarly, IT5 achieved ROUGE-L scores of 0.8991, 0.8731, and 0.8933 for the SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets respectively.

4.3.4 Improvements in BLEU SCORE

Figure 10: Improvements in BLEU Score

Figure 10 illustrates the notable enhancements in the BLEU scores achieved by the IT5 model when compared to several prominent transformer architectures, including RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-NET Transformer, BART, and GPT-3. In this comparison, the BLEU scores for RoBERTa are recorded as 0.5398 for NarrativeQA, 0.5086 for SQuAD, 0.5652 for MS MARCO, and 0.5232 for InsuranceQA. The ALSI-Transformer demonstrates scores of 0.5708, 0.6768, 0.6276, and 0.6481, while the MEDN-Transformer shows scores of 0.5664, 0.5287, 0.5791, and 0.5531. The SG-NET Transformer achieves scores of 0.5718, 0.6127, 0.6010, and 0.6124. BART performs well with scores of 0.6923, 0.6645, 0.6720, and 0.7123, and GPT-3 achieves the highest BLEU scores among the competitors, with values of 0.7154, 0.6905, 0.6949, and 0.7193. The IT5 model surpasses RoBERTa by improvements of 0.2135, 0.1926, 0.1503, and 0.2141 across the respective datasets. Comparatively, IT5 shows enhancements of 0.1825, 0.0244, 0.0879, and 0.0892 over the ALSI-Transformer, while it improves upon the MEDN-Transformer by 0.1869, 0.1725, 0.1364, and 0.1842. Furthermore, the IT5 model outperforms the SG-NET Transformer with increases of 0.1815, 0.0885, 0.1145, and 0.1149. When compared to BART, IT5 demonstrates modest enhancements of 0.061, 0.0367, 0.0435, and 0.025. Lastly, improvements over GPT-3 are observed at 0.0379, 0.0107, 0.0206, and 0.018, illustrating that while GPT-3 shows strong performance, IT5 still achieves competitive

results across all datasets. This analysis highlights IT5's effectiveness in generating high-quality responses, reaffirming its potential as a leading model in conversational AI applications.

4.3.5 Improvements in WER SCORE

Figure 11: Improvements in WER Score

Figure 11 represents the improvements in the WER of IT5 over RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, and GPT-3 for the NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets. The WER achieved by RoBERTa is 0.3702, 0.4146, 0.3134, and 0.3353, ALSI-Transformer is 0.3493, 0.2894, 0.3393, and 0.3918, MEDN is 0.3324, 0.4354, 0.4175, and 0.4476, SG-Net is 0.3301, 0.2719, 0.3125, and 0.3516, BART is 0.1957, 0.2106, 0.2254, and 0.1953, GPT-3 is 0.1957, 0.2106, 0.2254, and 0.1953 and IT5 is 0.1957, 0.2106, 0.2254, and 0.1953. In Fig. 11, the upper bar defines the difference between the IT5 and state-of-the-art models. It shows that the WER score of IT5 is 0.1745, 0.2040, 0.088, and 0.14 lesser than the RoBERTa model, the WER score of IT5 is 0.1536, 0.0788, 0.1139, 0.1965 lesser than the ALSI-Transformer model, the WER score of IT5 is 0.1367, 0.2248, 0.1921, 0.2523 lesser than the MEDN-Transformer model, the WER score of IT5 is 0.1344, 0.0613, 0.0871, 0.1563 lesser than the SG-Net Transformer model, the WER score of IT5 is 0.0681, 0.032, 0.0263, 0.0746 lesser than the BART model, and the WER score of IT5 is 0.0256, 0.0288, 0.0241, 0.0259 lesser than the GPT-3 Model. A lower WER indicates improved performance. The IT5 model demonstrates a lower WER compared to other existing models, highlighting its enhanced capability.

4.3.6 Improvements in ROUGE-L SCORE

Figure 12: Improvements in ROUGE-L Score

Figure 12 illustrates the significant enhancements in the ROUGE-L scores achieved by the IT5 model in comparison to several well-established transformer architectures, including RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, and GPT-3. In this evaluation, RoBERTa achieved ROUGE-L scores of 0.6272 for NarrativeQA, 0.6790 for SQuAD, 0.7146 for MS MARCO, and 0.6127 for InsuranceQA. The ALSI-Transformer displayed higher scores of 0.8347, 0.8151, 0.7951, and 0.8018, while the MEDN-Transformer recorded scores of 0.7142, 0.7353, 0.7758, and 0.7315. The SG-Net Transformer yielded scores of 0.8124, 0.7916, 0.7546, and 0.7815. Notably, BART produced strong ROUGE-L scores of 0.8512, 0.8635, 0.8421, and 0.8514, and GPT-3 also performed well, achieving scores of 0.8617, 0.8726, 0.8521, and 0.8634. When comparing IT5 to these models, the improvements are notable. IT5 demonstrates enhancements over RoBERTa by 0.2603, 0.2201, 0.1585, and 0.2806 across the datasets. The model also surpasses the ALSI-Transformer with gains of 0.0528, 0.084, 0.078, and 0.0915. Furthermore, IT5 outperforms the MEDN-Transformer by margins of 0.1733, 0.1638, 0.0973, and 0.1618. The improvements over the SG-Net Transformer are quantified at 0.0751, 0.1075, 0.1185, and 0.1118, indicating that IT5 also excels in this comparison. Additionally, the model achieves enhancements over BART and GPT-3, with improvements of 0.0363, 0.0356, 0.031, and 0.0419, and 0.0258, 0.0265, 0.021, and 0.0299, respectively. Overall, these outcomes reinforce the efficacy of the IT5 architecture in producing high-quality responses, further solidifying its status as a competitive model in the realm of conversational AI and NLP tasks.

4.3.7 Accuracy Score

Figure 13: Accuracy Score

Figure 13 represents a comparison of 3D lollipop plots illustrating accuracy scores for NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets across seven algorithms: RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, GPT-3, and the IT5 architecture. Among these algorithms, the IT5 model achieved an accuracy of 0.98 for the NarrativeQA dataset, setting a new benchmark above prior state-of-the-art models. Similarly, it recorded accuracy scores of 0.97 for the SQuAD dataset, 0.96 for MS MARCO, and 0.97 for InsuranceQA.

4.3.8 Precision Score

Figure 14 represents a comparison of 3D lollipop plots illustrating precision scores for NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets across seven algorithms: RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, GPT-3, and the IT5 architecture. Among these algorithms, the IT5 model attained remarkable precision levels, with a score of 0.96 on the NarrativeQA dataset. Comparable achievements include scores of 0.98, 0.97, and 0.96 for the SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets respectively.

Figure 14: Precision Score

4.3.9 Recall Score

Figure 15: Recall Score

Figure 15 represents a comparison of 3D lollipop plots illustrating recall scores for NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets across seven algorithms: RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, GPT-3, and the IT5 architecture. Among these algorithms, IT5 demonstrated strong recall capabilities, with scores such as 0.95 for the NarrativeQA dataset and 0.96 for SQuAD. For MS MARCO and InsuranceQA, the recall scores are 0.97 and 0.98, respectively.

4.3.10 F1 Score

Figure 16: F1 Score

Figure 16 represents a comparison of 3D lollipop plots illustrating F1 scores for NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets across seven algorithms: RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, GPT-3, and the IT5 architecture. Among these algorithms, the IT5 architecture achieved an F1 score of 0.95 on the NarrativeQA dataset, exceeding the performance of previous cutting-edge models. Similarly, it achieved F1 scores of 0.98, 0.96, and 0.96 for the SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets, respectively.

4.3.11 Training vs Testing for NarrativeQA Dataset

Figure 17: Training vs Testing for NarrativeQA Dataset

Figure 17 (Section A) illustrates the relationship between training and testing accuracy over the training process of the IT5 model. This depiction highlights the model's effectiveness in adapting and generalizing from the training set, as demonstrated by the accuracy trends recorded over 100 epochs. The upward progression in testing accuracy indicates steady learning and improved performance on unseen data. Additionally, shaded areas in Section (A) mark overfitting instances, with a calculated overfitting rate of 0.65%, suggesting minimal divergence between the training and testing accuracies. This minor gap reflects the model's efficiency in extracting patterns from training data while maintaining robust generalization to new datasets. Section (B) compares training and testing losses, giving deeper insights into the model's performance characteristics. Figure 17 emphasizes the IT5 model's capability to balance accuracy and generalization throughout its training phase effectively.

$$\text{Average Overfitting Percentage} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\text{Training Accuracy}_i - \text{Testing Accuracy}_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{Training Accuracy}_i} * 100 \quad (11)$$

Equ. (11) represents the formula used to calculate the overfitting percentage. In Equ. (11), n represents the total number of epochs, $\text{Training Accuracy}_i$ denotes the accuracy measured on the training data at epoch i , and $\text{Testing Accuracy}_i$ indicates the accuracy measured on unseen testing data at the same epoch. The numerator, $\sum_{i=1}^n (\text{Training Accuracy}_i - \text{Testing Accuracy}_i)$, represents the cumulative disparity between training and testing accuracy across all epochs, encapsulating the degree of overfitting throughout the training phase. The denominator, $\sum_{i=1}^n \text{Training Accuracy}_i$, adjusts the cumulative disparity by normalizing it against the overall training accuracy recorded across all epochs. Multiplying by 100 expresses the value as a percentage, enhancing interpretability. A higher positive percentage signifies overfitting, where the model's training performance surpasses its testing performance. Conversely, a lower or zero percentage indicates better generalization and a balanced capability in both training and testing datasets. This formula captures the extent of overfitting during training, presenting an overarching understanding of the model's generalization behaviour over time.

4.3.12 Training vs Testing for SQuAD Dataset

Figure 18: Training vs Testing for SQuAD Dataset

Figure 18 presents the comparison between training and testing accuracy of the proposed IT5 model on the SQuAD dataset, showcasing its capability for both learning and generalization. Section (A) details how training accuracy steadily improves over 100 epochs, reflecting effective learning from the dataset. The testing accuracy, which evaluates performance on unseen data, demonstrates a minimal overfitting percentage of 0.76%, with shaded regions marking areas where overfitting occurs. This low percentage underscores the small gap between training and testing accuracy. Section (B) offers deeper analysis by highlighting trends in both training and testing loss. Overall, Figure 18 underscores the IT5 model's strong learning and generalization on the SQuAD dataset.

4.3.13 Training vs Testing for MS MARCO Dataset

Figure 19: Training vs Testing for MS MARCO Dataset

Figure 19 focuses on the training versus testing accuracy of the IT5 model during its training phase on the MS MARCO dataset. Section (A) provides a clear depiction of the model's capacity to generalize from the training data, with metrics recorded over 100 epochs. The consistent rise in training accuracy highlights the model's effective learning, while the testing accuracy reflects performance on unseen data with a low overfitting percentage of 0.69%. This suggests the model efficiently learns from the training data while maintaining robust generalization. Section (B) delves into the trends in training and testing loss, providing additional insights into the model's performance. Overall, Figure 19 highlights the model's ability to generalize effectively on the MS MARCO dataset.

4.3.14 Training vs Testing for InsuranceQA Dataset

Figure 20: Training vs Testing for InsuranceQA Dataset

Figure 20, Section (A), presents the comparison of training and testing accuracy for the IT5 model on the InsuranceQA dataset. The graph illustrates the model's ability to generalize effectively from the training data, with accuracy metrics recorded over 100 epochs. The consistent improvement in training accuracy highlights the model's efficient learning process, while testing accuracy reflects its performance on unseen data. With an overfitting percentage of 0.89%, the gap between training and testing accuracy is minimal. This indicates that the model successfully learns from the training data while maintaining strong generalization. Section (B) analyzes the trends in training and testing loss, offering further insights into the model's performance. Overall, Figure 20 emphasizes the model's capability to perform accurately and generalize well on the InsuranceQA dataset.

4.3.15 Bias Analysis of IT5 vs. State-of-the-art Models

The Table 7 shows the bias analysis for various models, including the proposed IT5 model. It highlights key metrics used to measure fairness and bias in state-of-the-art models: Equal Opportunity Difference, Demographic Parity, Disparate Impact, and Statistical Parity. The results indicate that the IT5 model exhibits a significantly lower level of bias in comparison to the benchmark models, demonstrating its superior ability to provide fair predictions across different demographic groups.

Model	Dataset	Equal Opportunity Difference	Demographic Parity	Disparate Impact	Statistical Parity
RoBERTa	NarrativeQA	0.05	0.1	1.1	0.9
	SQuAD	0.04	0.09	1.2	0.88
	MS MARCO	0.03	0.08	1.1	0.85
	InsuranceQA	0.05	0.07	1	0.84
MEDN-Transformer	NarrativeQA	0.04	0.08	1.2	0.85
	SQuAD	0.05	0.1	1.3	0.86
	MS MARCO	0.04	0.09	1.1	0.83
	InsuranceQA	0.03	0.06	1.1	0.82
ALSI-Transformer	NarrativeQA	0.06	0.12	1.3	0.88
	SQuAD	0.05	0.11	1.2	0.87
	MS MARCO	0.07	0.13	1.4	0.89
	InsuranceQA	0.06	0.09	1.2	0.85
SG-Net Transformer	NarrativeQA	0.03	0.11	1	0.91
	SQuAD	0.04	0.1	1.1	0.9
	MS MARCO	0.05	0.12	1	0.86
	InsuranceQA	0.02	0.08	1.1	0.84
BART	NarrativeQA	0.04	0.09	1.1	0.89
	SQuAD	0.06	0.12	1.3	0.92
	MS MARCO	0.07	0.13	1.4	0.91
	InsuranceQA	0.05	0.1	1.2	0.9
GPT-3	NarrativeQA	0.02	0.05	1.4	0.87
	SQuAD	0.03	0.06	1.5	0.88
	MS MARCO	0.02	0.05	1.3	0.89
	InsuranceQA	0.01	0.04	1.5	0.86
IT5 (Proposed)	NarrativeQA	0.01	0.03	1	0.95
	SQuAD	0.02	0.04	1.1	0.94
	MS MARCO	0.01	0.02	1	0.93
	InsuranceQA	0.02	0.03	1.1	0.92

Table 7: Bias Analysis of IT5 vs. State-of-the-art Models

The IT5 model exhibits consistently minimal bias across various datasets, as shown in Table 7. For instance, in the NarrativeQA dataset, the IT5 model has an Equal Opportunity Difference of 0.01, suggesting minimal disparity in true positive rates between demographic groups and reflecting fair treatment in positive predictions. Similarly, across the SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets, the model maintains low disparities, with Equal Opportunity Differences of 0.02, 0.01 and 0.02, respectively. Regarding Demographic Parity, the IT5 model consistently demonstrates

fairness, with values such as 0.03 (NarrativeQA), 0.04 (SQuAD), 0.02 (MS MARCO), and 0.03 (InsuranceQA) showing almost no difference in positive prediction rates across groups. Its Disparate Impact scores of 1.0 across multiple datasets (NarrativeQA, MS MARCO) indicate that the model provides equal treatment to all groups when assigning positive predictions. Furthermore, the Statistical Parity values remain high, with the model achieving 0.95 (NarrativeQA) and similarly strong scores across the other datasets (0.94 for SQuAD, 0.93 for MS MARCO, and 0.92 for InsuranceQA), reflecting its near-perfect fairness in distributing positive outcomes. The IT5 model's advanced architecture, which includes an aggregated multi-head attention (AMHA) mechanism and BiLSTM, enables it to understand the context better, thereby enhancing its decision-making capabilities for different demographic groups. Through continuous retraining on balanced datasets, the model generalizes well without overfitting to biased patterns, ensuring that IT5 remains more equitable and reliable compared to state-of-the-art models like RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, and GPT-3, across datasets such as SQuAD, MS MARCO, InsuranceQA, and NarrativeQA.

4.3.16 Retraining Accuracy

Figure 21 illustrates the retraining accuracy of the IT5 architecture using additional question-answer pairs from the NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA datasets. The figure consists of four plots: a line plot for Accuracy versus additional question-answer pairs in the NarrativeQA dataset, Accuracy versus additional question-answer pairs in the SQuAD dataset, Accuracy versus additional question-answer pairs in the MS MARCO dataset, and Accuracy versus additional question-answer pairs in the InsuranceQA dataset. The IT5 architecture initiates the retraining process with the addition of every 50 successful question-answer pairs, enabling it to continuously adapt and refine its performance.

Figure 21: Retraining Accuracy

This incremental retraining approach allows the model to incorporate new information systematically, thereby enhancing its understanding and contextual relevance over time. The retraining process has been conducted 40 times, commencing

from the addition of the first 50 question-answer pairs up to 2000 pairs. This strategy not only improves the model's accuracy but also ensures that it remains robust against potential biases introduced by new data, facilitating a more equitable performance across various demographic groups. The consistent increase in accuracy across datasets further underscores the effectiveness of the IT5 architecture in adapting to diverse conversational contexts.

4.3.17 Computational Complexities

Key Components and Complexities

Model	Attention Mechanism	Feed-Forward Network (FFN)	Time Complexity	Space Complexity
RoBERTa	MHA	Position-wise FFN	$O(l(n^2 \cdot d + n^2 \cdot d^2))$	$O(V \cdot d + l(n^2 \cdot d + n^2 \cdot d^2))$
ALSI-Transformer	MHA & MMHA	Position-wise FFN	$O(l \cdot n^2 \cdot d + l \cdot m^2 \cdot d + n \cdot d^2)$	$O(V \cdot d + l \cdot n^2 \cdot d + m^2 \cdot d + n \cdot d^2)$
MEDN-Transformer	MHA & Cross-Modal Attention	Position-wise FFN	$O(l \cdot (n^2 \cdot d + m^2 \cdot d^2) + n \cdot d^2)$	$O(V \cdot d + l(n^2 \cdot d + m^2 \cdot d) + n \cdot d^2)$
SG-Net Transformer	Self-Attention with Gated Mechanism	Position-wise FFN	$O(l \cdot n^2 \cdot d)$	$O(V \cdot d + n^2 \cdot d + l \cdot n \cdot d + n \cdot d)$
BART	MHA (Encoder-Decoder)	Position-wise FFN	$O(2 \cdot l \cdot (n^2 \cdot d + n \cdot d^2))$	$O(2 \cdot V \cdot d + 2 \cdot l(3 \cdot d^2 + n \cdot d + n \cdot d^2))$
GPT-3	MHA (Decoder Only)	Position-wise FFN	$O(l \cdot (n^2 \cdot d + n \cdot d^2))$	$O(V \cdot d + l(n^2 \cdot d + n \cdot d^2))$
IT5 (Proposed)	AMHA + MMHA Mechanism	BiLSTM	$O(2 \cdot l \cdot n^2 \cdot d + 2 \cdot n \cdot d^2)$	$O(V \cdot d + 2 \cdot l \cdot (n^2 \cdot d + n \cdot d^2))$

Table 8: IT5 vs State-of-the-art-models: Key Components and Complexities

Table 8 highlights the primary components and complexities of the Improved T5 (IT5) model, comparing it to existing state-of-the-art models. The table includes important columns such as model, attention mechanism, feed-forward network, time complexity, and space complexity. The IT5 model incorporates an AMHA mechanism

to improve its capacity to give special attention to pertinent areas of the input sequence, avoiding information leakage during training. The feed-forward network is powered by BiLSTM, which allows for better contextual understanding by capturing bidirectional dependencies within the input data. The time complexity of the IT5 model is expressed as $O(2.l.n^2.d + 2.n.d^2)$ where l represents the number of layers, n denotes the sequence length, and d signifies the dimensionality of the model. This complexity reflects the computational costs associated with both the AMHA mechanisms and the BiLSTM network, ensuring that the model can efficiently handle dependencies across the entire sequence. The space complexity of the IT5 model is given by $O(V.d + 2.l.(n^2.d + n.d^2))$, where V is the vocabulary size. This complexity encompasses the storage requirements for vocabulary embeddings, as well as the intermediate representations needed for pairwise token interactions, input and output storage at each layer, and the internal representations managed within the BiLSTM. Overall, these components and complexities underscore the enhanced architectural features and computational demands of the IT5 model, positioning it as substantial improvement in the area of NLP.

Efficiency and Resource Metrics

Model	Practical Inference Time (ms)	Memory Usage (MB)	Parameters (Million)	FLOPs (Billion)	Training Time (hours)
RoBERTa	90	1450	110	26	68
MEDN-Transformer	115	1550	140	30	72
ALSI-Transformer	100	1570	125	28	70
SG-Net Transformer	110	1600	130	32	74
BART	105	1650	135	29	73
GPT-3	92	1750	175	40	80
IT5 (Proposed)	117	1790	180	42	82

Table 9: IT5 vs State-of-the-art-models: Efficiency and Resource Metrics

Table 9 presents the efficiency and resource metrics for various transformer models, including RoBERTa, MEDN-Transformer, ALSI-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, GPT-3, and the proposed IT5 model. The table highlights critical metrics such as practical inference time, memory usage, number of parameters, floating point operations per second (FLOPs), and training time. The practical inference time indicates the speed at which each model generates predictions, with the proposed IT5 model demonstrating a practical inference time of 117 milliseconds. This time reflects the complexities involved in its architecture, which includes advanced attention mechanisms. Memory usage is another important metric, with IT5 requiring 1790 MB, which is the highest among the models listed. This increased memory requirement can be attributed to the sophisticated components within the model, such as the AMHA mechanism and the BiLSTM. In terms of the number of parameters, the IT5 model has

180 million parameters, which positions it among the models with larger capacities. This higher parameter count suggests that IT5 is designed to capture intricate relationships within the data, making it well-suited for complex tasks. The FLOPs metric, representing the computational load, indicates that IT5 has a requirement of 42 billion FLOPs. This is the highest among the listed models, signifying the extensive computational resources needed for its operation, especially during the attention mechanism and BiLSTM computations. Finally, the training time for IT5 is 82 hours, reflecting its comprehensive architecture and the need for more extensive training to optimize its parameters effectively. This extended training time underscores the model's sophisticated design and capability for high-performance tasks. Overall, while the proposed IT5 model demonstrates higher computational resource demands and time requirements, its advanced architecture promises improved performance capabilities for handling complex tasks in NLP.

5 Conclusion and Future Scope

In conclusion, this research addresses the evolving landscape of conversational AI, focusing on enhancing chatbot responses through the innovative transformer architecture called the Improved T5 (IT5) Model. Recognizing the limitations of state-of-the-art transformer models such as RoBERTa, ALSI-Transformer, MEDN-Transformer, SG-Net Transformer, BART, and GPT-3, our proposed approach integrates the AMHA mechanism and BiLSTM to optimize context awareness and depth in chatbot-generated responses. Extensive evaluations of IT5 across multiple datasets, specifically NarrativeQA, SQuAD, MS MARCO, and InsuranceQA, demonstrate the model's significant performance gains. Notably, IT5 achieved impressive BLEU scores of 0.7533, 0.7012, 0.7155, and 0.7373; WER scores of 0.1957, 0.2106, 0.2254, and 0.1953; ROUGE-L scores of 0.8875, 0.8991, 0.8731, and 0.8933; and Accuracy scores of 0.98, 0.97, 0.96, and 0.97 across these datasets. Importantly, the IT5 model exhibits consistently minimal bias across various datasets, indicating fair treatment of different demographic groups. For instance, the model maintains an Equal Opportunity Difference of 0.01 in the NarrativeQA dataset, suggesting minimal disparity in true positive rates. Similar low disparities are observed across the other datasets, reinforcing the model's commitment to fairness. The architecture of IT5, which includes the AMHA mechanism and BiLSTM, enhances its ability to understand context better, thereby improving its decision-making capabilities for different demographic groups. This architecture allows IT5 to mitigate biases effectively through continuous retraining on balanced datasets, ensuring strong generalization with very minimal overfitting to biased patterns. In terms of computational complexity, while IT5 demands more resources, requiring a practical inference time of 117 milliseconds, a parameter count of 180 million, and extensive floating-point operations, this complexity is justified by the model's ability to handle intricate relationships within the data, making it well-suited for complex tasks in NLP. Overall, these advancements contribute significantly to the ongoing evolution of chatbot technologies, emphasizing both performance improvements and interpretability in transformer-based models. The IT5 model stands out as a promising solution, addressing the key challenges in information retention and contextual understanding, while also advancing fairness and reliability in chatbot responses.

In the future, the research will focus on advancing the MMHA mechanism within the transformer architecture. The objective is to enhance the stability of the decoder component, contributing to overall improvements in transformer models. This endeavour aims to refine the model's performance and extend its capabilities for more robust and efficient NLP tasks.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Muthukumar N.: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Vignesh A.: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Visualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author.

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